

Report on segmentation of energy consumers and preferences of each segment

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Report on segmentation of energy consumers and
preferences of each segment

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Nature of the deliverable		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	X
CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	

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Executive summary

In two large scale surveys conducted in Spain (n = 1334) and the United Kingdom (n = 1809), we study consumer willingness to adopt services and products that can aid in building demand-side flexibility in energy markets.

We first focus on an example of mobile phone apps that can help consumers to track, better understand, and manage their energy consumption. We observe that perceived environmental, functional, and symbolic benefits of these apps increase the willingness to use them. This finding therefore demonstrates that it is not only the functional properties but also the less tangible benefits that can increase product adoption. Perhaps surprisingly, there are not very pronounced differences in consumers' valuation of these benefits, although we, for example, find that environmentally conscious consumers value environmental benefits of these products more (which is intuitive) and that women and relatively older people value functional performance of these products more. Marketing efforts highlighting specific benefits of these products can be therefore tailored to these consumer segments. Our results also show that consumer segments that are overall most likely to adopt energy monitoring mobile phone apps consist of individuals who are more environmentally concerned, innovative, younger, wealthier, living in larger households, and female.

We next focus on electricity contracts featuring attributes consistent with a shift towards a more flexible energy demand. People prefer electricity contracts offering an increased share of renewable energy and greater financial savings (the latter is especially true for men compared to women). People in the UK are generally averse to electricity services enabling their electricity provider to directly control their thermostat during evening demand peaks in winter. This aversion is more pronounced for people above 50, for people with weak perceived moral obligation to protect the environment, and also for people who perceive themselves as environmentally friendly. Surprisingly, people in Spain are on average happy to give up control of their thermostat to their electricity provider during evening demand peaks in winter (less so in case of people who see themselves as environmentally friendly and people with eco-friendly consumption habits). Surprisingly, consumers do not find energy services bundled with technologies giving them the option to remotely control their electrical appliances attractive.

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1. Introduction

Demand-side flexibility contributes to balancing energy supply and demand, and is becoming increasingly important with the rise of intermittent renewable energy generation in Europe. This report presents results from two empirical studies looking at aspects of consumer willingness to engage in demand-side flexibility. We investigate which service and product attributes may motivate consumers to take steps towards engaging in demand response.

Mobile phone apps increasing awareness of own energy usage and allowing control of own household appliances are one tool that can help consumers engage in demand response. Building on previous research on eco-friendly technology adoption (e.g., Noppers et al., 2014, 2015; Whittle et al., 2020), we explore and confirm that perceived environmental, functional, and symbolic attributes (or benefits) of such mobile phone apps are associated with interest in using this type of product.

Existing research identified promising consumer segments most likely to adopt eco-friendly technologies. These consumer groups consist of people who are more environmentally conscious (e.g., van der Werff & Steg, 2016), who feel intrinsic or social pressure to behave sustainably (e.g., van der Werff & Steg, 2016; Hmielowski et al., 2019), or who are innovative (e.g., Noppers et al., 2015). Our study focusing on energy monitoring apps identifies partly similar consumer segments likely to adopt this type of technology (e.g., environmentally concerned and innovative consumers are more likely to adopt).

Previous research also started dissecting which consumer segments are most responsive to which attributes of eco-friendly technologies. Functional attributes of smart thermostats, such as remote temperature control and energy use tracking functionalities, are for example more important to innovative consumers (Tu et al., 2021). We systematically explore potential differences in valuation of product attributes among different consumer segments. Our data point to only a small number of such differences, with gender, age, home ownership, environmental concern and social norms influencing consumer preferences for specific product attributes (e.g., performance vs. environmental benefits).

We next look, using data from two choice experiments, at how different features of energy services can influence service uptake. Existing research from a dozen mostly European countries shows that without some form of compensation or added benefit, consumers are on average unwilling to engage in demand response (e.g., Broberg & Persson, 2016; Ruokamo et al., 2019). Financial savings (e.g., Broberg & Persson, 2016) or an increased share of renewable energy (e.g., Lehmann et al., 2021) may nevertheless compensate perceived disadvantages of engaging in demand response. We confirm that consumers derive utility from an increased share of renewable energy and from financial savings. Somewhat surprisingly, we find that technological innovations, namely giving consumers the ability to remotely manage their appliances, may not be useful in terms of motivating people to engage in demand response. We study acceptance of direct load control specifically by looking at preferences for direct load control of thermostat in winter. In line with previous research, we observe that people in the UK prefer not giving up flexibility in heating use. In contrast, people in Spain are happy to give up flexibility in heating use (perhaps because of the milder winter climate).

A few studies explored differences in valuation of features of energy services by different consumer groups. For example environmentally conscious consumers (Curtis et al., 2020), relatively older people (Broberg & Persson, 2016; Curtis et al., 2020), men (Broberg & Persson, 2016; Lehmann et al., 2022a), and urban residents (Lim et al., 2021) may be more inclined to accept energy services involving direct load control. Extending this nascent line of research, we examine the potential influence of selected socio-demographic and attitudinal variables on people's preferences for different features of energy services.

2. Research questions and research background

In this section we present our five main research questions, the first two dealing with willingness to enroll in energy services involving demand response, the remaining three dealing with the adoption of energy monitoring apps. We place each research question in a context of relevant former research. We then divide each research question into a set of testable predictions. The predictions will be tested using methods and procedures outlined in section 3., with test results presented in section 4. and their implications discussed in section 5.

2.1. Consumer preferences for energy services: The role of service attributes

Research question 1: How do attributes of energy services – in particular, attainable financial savings, share of electricity generated from renewable sources, remote control of household appliances, and energy provider's ability to control the consumer's thermostat during demand peaks – affect consumer preferences for the services?

2.1.1. Former research

Several studies show that consumers on average dislike energy services enabling external control of their energy consumption ("direct load control") during demand peaks. See Srivastava et al. (2020) for evidence from Belgium, Ladenburg et al. (2022) for evidence from Denmark, Ruokamo et al. (2019) for evidence from Finland, Lehmann et al. (2022a) for evidence from Germany¹, Richter and Pollitt (2018) for evidence from Great Britain, Harold et al. (2021) for evidence from Ireland, Gołębiewska et al. (2021) for evidence from Poland, Broberg and Persson (2016) and Broberg et al. (2021) for evidence from Sweden, Moser (2017), Kubli et al. (2018), and Yilmaz et al. (2021) for evidence from Switzerland², Toccock et al. (2023) for evidence from Australia, Lim et al. (2021) for evidence from South Korea, and Xu et al. (2018) and Kaczmarek et al. (2022) for evidence from the United States.

Consumers, on the other hand, prefer energy services that promise higher shares of energy generated from renewable sources (e.g., Bailey & Axsen, 2015; Kubli et al., 2018; Lehmann et al., 2021; Fait et al., 2022; Will et al., 2022; Toccock et al., 2023), emission reductions (Longo et al., 2008; Shin et al., 2014; Ruokamo et al., 2019), and financial savings (e.g., Broberg & Persson, 2016; Richter & Pollitt, 2018; Ruokamo et al., 2019; Srivastava et al., 2020; Broberg et al., 2021; Harold et al.,

¹ Sundt et al. (2020) report mixed findings from Germany.

² Ludwig and Winzer (2022) report inconclusive findings from Switzerland.

2021). Innovations allowing consumers to remotely monitor and control their appliances are also regarded positively (Tu et al., 2021; Chappin et al., 2022).

Additional important characteristics of energy services which are, however, outside the scope of the present research, include for example dynamic pricing (e.g., Buryk et al., 2015; Ruokamo et al., 2019; Sundt et al., 2020; Ludwig & Winzer, 2022; von Loessl, 2023), protection of privacy (e.g., Broberg & Persson, 2016; Richter & Pollitt, 2018; Gołębiowska et al., 2021; Lim et al., 2021; von Loessl, 2023), and electricity supply reliability (e.g., Longo et al., 2008; Shin et al., 2014; Ozbaflı & Jenkins, 2016; Cohen et al., 2018; Srivastava et al., 2021).

We build on existing research in formulating our first research question (see above). We rely on the discrete choice experimental methodology which, while enabling causal inference, is limited in the number of service attributes that can be studied concurrently in a single experiment. For that reason we focus on a selection of four key attributes. Financial savings, positive environmental impact (in our case, consuming energy from renewables), and user convenience (in our case, the ability to remotely control own electric appliances) are three attributes of energy services that we expect may increase demand for the service, while energy provider's control of the consumer's thermostat is likely to have the opposite effect (although prediction P4 is non-directional).

2.1.2. Testable predictions

We decompose our first research question into the following four predictions.

P1: "Financial savings" increase "preferences for energy service".³

P2: "Renewable sources share" increases "preferences for energy service".

P3: "Remote control of appliances" increases "preferences for energy service".

P4: "Energy provider control of thermostat" predicts "preferences for energy service".

2.2. Consumer preferences for energy services: Exploring preference heterogeneity

Research question 2: Do consumers differ in terms of the weight they place on the different attributes of energy services (specifically on financial savings, share of renewables, remote control of appliances, and on relinquishing control of thermostat during demand peaks)?

2.2.1. Former research

Vesely et al. (2022), among others, advocate for studying the heterogeneity in responses different consumer groups may have to policy, market and social influences, such as incentives and social norms, in the context of energy consumption and energy efficiency investments. A good understanding of the responsiveness of different consumer segments to energy service attributes is similarly important. Design and marketing of energy services may be, as a result, better tailored to

³ Throughout this document, variable names often appear in quotation marks for clarity. Variable operationalizations can be found in section 3.2.

the needs of specific consumer groups. Marketing efforts targeting consumers who are for example largely indifferent to financial savings but place value on consuming energy generated from renewable sources, may differ from marketing strategies targeting consumers for whom financial savings are the main priority.

Existing research on consumer preferences for energy services enabling demand response does not offer sufficiently systematic insights into how different consumer groups respond to different features or attributes of these services, which is a research gap we address in our two choice experiments.

In an early study, Broberg and Persson (2016), nevertheless, report that aversion to direct load control is increasing with income and is directly related to gender, as women are more averse to it. On the other hand, aversion to direct load control decreases with age,. Curtis et al. (2020) find that acceptance of more frequent direct load control events increases with age and with environmental attitude; multi-person households in addition exhibit stronger preferences for having the option to opt out of load curtailment events than single-person households. Echoing the two studies just mentioned, Srivastava et al. (2020) and Lehmann et al. (2022a) again report older participants being more accepting of more frequent direct load control events. Lehmann et al. (2022a) in addition, observe that more educated respondents and women dislike increases in frequency of energy use quota events, the latter finding echoing a similar result from Broberg and Persson (2016). Lim et al. (2021) find that metropolitan residents are more accepting of direct load control than non-metropolitan residents.

People with stronger environmental values (Bailey & Axsen, 2015; Lehmann et al., 2022b) and higher educational achievement (Bailey & Axsen, 2015) respond more positively than others to services offering higher shares of renewable energy. Lehmann et al. (2021) find that women and younger people value energy generated from renewable sources more than men and older consumers; the correlation of preferences for renewable energy with gender being potentially mediated via environmental values, as it disappears or can even be reversed once environmental values are controlled (Lehmann et al., 2022b).

In summary, older participants, men, environmentally conscious consumers, urban residents, the less wealthy and the less educated tentatively emerge from previously conducted studies as the consumer segments that are more inclined to accept energy services involving direct load control. Women, younger participants, the more educated, and environmentally conscious consumers may value renewable energy more than other consumer groups. These conclusions are based on a small set of initial studies, and require replication before firmer conclusions can be drawn.

2.2.2. Testable predictions

We again decompose the above research question into a series of testable predictions.

P5: “Financial savings” interact with “gender” in predicting “preferences for energy service”.

P6: “Financial savings” interact with “age” in predicting “preferences for energy service”.

P7: “Financial savings” interact with “education” in predicting “preferences for energy service”.

P8: "Renewable sources share" interacts with "gender" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P9: "Renewable sources share" interacts with "age" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P10: "Renewable sources share" interacts with "education" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P11: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "environmental concern" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P12: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "environmental identity" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P13: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "personal norm" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P14: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "pro-environmental consumer habits" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P15: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "descriptive social norm" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P16: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "injunctive social norm" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P17: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "gender" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P18: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "age" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P19: "Remote control of appliances" interacts with "education" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P20: "Energy provider control of thermostat" interacts with "environmental concern" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P21: "Energy provider control of thermostat" interacts with "environmental identity" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P22: "Energy provider control of thermostat" interacts with "personal norm" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P23: "Energy provider control of thermostat" interacts with "pro-environmental consumer habits" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P24: "Energy provider control of thermostat" interacts with "descriptive social norm" in predicting "preferences for energy service".

P25: “Energy provider control of thermostat” interacts with “injunctive social norm” in predicting “preferences for energy service”.

P26: “Energy provider control of thermostat” interacts with “gender” in predicting “preferences for energy service”.

P27: “Energy provider control of thermostat” interacts with “age” in predicting “preferences for energy service”.

2.3. Consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices: The role of perceived product attributes

Research question 3: How do perceived attributes of apps monitoring energy consumption of electrical appliances in one’s household – specifically environmental, instrumental, and symbolic attributes – influence consumer preferences for such devices?

2.3.1. Former research

Previous research on eco-friendly technology adoption indicates that perceived product attributes may be a key factor influencing consumption decisions.

Environmental attributes of products are associated with adoption⁴ of electric vehicles (Noppers et al., 2014, 2015, 2019), home energy management systems (Park et al., 2017), and with intentions to use local renewable energy systems (Noppers et al., 2014).

Similarly, instrumental attributes, such as convenience, performance and cost, are associated with adoption of electric vehicles (Schuitema et al., 2013; Noppers et al., 2015; Schmalfuß et al., 2017; White & Sintov, 2017; Haustein et al., 2021; Salari, 2022), residential solar panels (Wolske et al., 2017; Lundheim et al., 2021), smart meters (Chen et al., 2017), smart thermostats (Girod et al., 2017), smart heating systems (Bielig et al., 2023), and home energy management systems (Park et al., 2017; Whittle et al., 2020).

Likewise, symbolic attributes, including opportunities for self-expression through product ownership and social emotions (e.g., pride) tied to product ownership, can influence electric car adoption (Schuitema et al., 2013; Noppers et al., 2014, 2015, 2019; White & Sintov, 2017; Sintov et al., 2020), intention to use local renewable energy systems (Noppers et al., 2014), and adoption of smart home energy systems (Noppers et al., 2016, 2019; Whittle et al., 2020).

Our study continues this line of research by investigating the role of product attributes in shaping consumer interest in devices (e.g., mobile phone apps) that can help track, control and better understand one’s energy consumption. For example results reported in Harding and Lamarche (2016) and Bollinger and Hartmann (2020) suggest that devices like these can usefully complement other policy instruments such as time-of-use pricing, as financial instruments alone may be less effective when consumers are not sufficiently aware of their energy usage patterns and how these may interact with fluctuations in energy price.

⁴ The cited studies typically do not record actual purchase decisions, but rather intentions, stated preferences or interest. We use the term “adoption” as a simplification.

2.3.2. Testable predictions

The above research question can be answered by testing the three predictions below.

P29: “Environmental attributes” increase “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P30: “Instrumental attributes” increase “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P31: “Symbolic attributes” increase “preferences for monitoring devices”.

2.4. Consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices: The role of consumer characteristics

Research question 4: Do consumer characteristics predict preferences for energy monitoring devices?

2.4.1. Former research

The literature on sustainable technology adoption attests to the importance of psychological factors in shaping purchase and use decisions, including environmental concern, environmental identity and sustainable consumer habits (e.g., van der Werff & Steg, 2016; Chen et al., 2017; Hmielowski et al., 2019; Mundaca & Samahita, 2020; Salari, 2022; Schulte et al., 2022), innovativeness (e.g., Noppers et al., 2015; Girod et al., 2017; Park et al., 2017; Wolske et al., 2017; Lundheim et al., 2021; Ho, 2022; Neves et al., 2022; Salari, 2022; Schulte et al., 2022), personal norms (e.g., van der Werff & Steg, 2016; Girod et al., 2017; Wolske et al., 2017; Yoon, 2018; Thøgersen & Ebsen, 2019; Taso et al., 2020; Hausteine et al., 2021; Neves et al., 2022), and social norms (e.g., Girod et al., 2017; Schmalfuß et al., 2017; Wolske et al., 2017; Yoon, 2018; Hmielowski et al., 2019; Noppers et al., 2019; Thøgersen & Ebsen, 2019; Chen et al., 2020; Taso et al., 2020; Hausteine et al., 2021; Neves et al., 2022; Schulte et al., 2022; Yew et al., 2022). The role of socio-demographic factors is generally less central, although they should not be disregarded (Kastner & Stern, 2015; Girod et al., 2017; Hmielowski et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020; Mundaca & Samahita, 2020; Neves et al., 2022; Schulte et al., 2022). We extend this line of study to consumer interest in devices that allow tracking, control and can improve awareness of one’s energy consumption.

2.4.2. Testable predictions

P32: “Environmental concern” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P33: “Environmental identity” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P34: “Innovativeness” increases “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P35: “Personal norm” increases “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P36: “Pro-environmental consumer habits” predict “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P37: “Descriptive social norm” increases “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P38: “Injunctive social norm” increases “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P39: “Gender” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P40: “Age” decreases “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P41: “Education” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P42: “Income” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P43: “Type of residence” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P44: “Home ownership” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P45: “Household size” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P46: “Region” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P47: “Place of residence size” predicts “preferences for monitoring devices”.

2.5. Consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices: Exploring preference heterogeneity

Research question 5: Do consumers differ in terms of the weight they place on the different attributes of energy monitoring devices (specifically on environmental, instrumental, and symbolic attributes)?

2.5.1. Former research

Research question 5 is similar to our research question 2, only this time focusing on consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices. The points we raised in section 2.2.1 are therefore also relevant here. A better understanding of how consumers differ in their valuation of various product attributes, such as price (an instrumental attribute) or self-expression (a symbolic attribute) would once again make it possible to better match marketing and/or design of product features to specific consumer groups.

Previous research is largely silent on how consumers differ in their valuation of instrumental, environmental and symbolic attributes of products such as energy monitoring and control devices. Nonetheless, Tu et al. (2021) show that instrumental attributes of smart thermostats, such as heating cost savings, remote temperature control, and energy use feedback functionalities, are more important to innovative consumers (and to environmentally conscious consumers, in case of heating cost savings). Results from Noppers et al. (2015) suggest that when considering an electric car purchase, more innovative consumers may weigh environmental, symbolic, and instrumental attributes slightly differently than more conservative consumers. Noppers et al. (2019) in addition suggest that the influence of symbolic product attributes may depend on perceived social norms. These and other similar interactive relationships are evaluated in the present study more systematically (see below) in the context of interest in energy monitoring devices.

2.5.2. Testable predictions

We derived the following predictions to address Research question 5.

P48: “Environmental attributes” interact with “environmental concern” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P49: “Environmental attributes” interact with “environmental identity” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P50: “Environmental attributes” interact with “innovativeness” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P51: “Environmental attributes” interact with “personal norm” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P52: “Environmental attributes” interact with “pro-environmental consumer habits” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P53: “Environmental attributes” interact with “descriptive social norm” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P54: “Environmental attributes” interact with “injunctive social norm” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P55: “Environmental attributes” interact with “gender” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P56: “Environmental attributes” interact with “age” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P57: “Environmental attributes” interact with “education” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P58: “Environmental attributes” interact with “income” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P59: “Environmental attributes” interact with “type of residence” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P60: “Environmental attributes” interact with “home ownership” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P61: “Environmental attributes” interact with “household size” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P62: “Environmental attributes” interact with “region” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P63: “Environmental attributes” interact with “place of residence size” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P64: “Instrumental attributes” interact with “environmental concern” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P65: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "environmental identity" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P66: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "innovativeness" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P67: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "personal norm" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P68: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "pro-environmental consumer habits" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P69: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "descriptive social norm" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P70: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "injunctive social norm" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P71: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "gender" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P72: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "age" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P73: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "education" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P74: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "income" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P75: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "type of residence" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P76: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "home ownership" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P77: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "household size" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P78: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "region" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P79: "Instrumental attributes" interact with "place of residence size" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P80: "Symbolic attributes" interact with "environmental concern" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P81: "Symbolic attributes" interact with "environmental identity" in predicting "preferences for monitoring devices".

P82: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “innovativeness” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P83: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “personal norm” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P84: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “pro-environmental consumer habits” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P85: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “descriptive social norm” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P86: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “injunctive social norm” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P87: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “gender” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P88: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “age” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P89: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “education” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P90: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “income” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P91: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “type of residence” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P92: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “home ownership” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P93: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “household size” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P94: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “region” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

P95: “Symbolic attributes” interact with “place of residence size” in predicting “preferences for monitoring devices”.

3. Method

We conducted two surveys (referred to as Study 1 and Study 2 in what follows) to address our research questions.

3.1. Participants

Study 1 was conducted online in 2022, with a convenience sample of United Kingdom residents recruited from Prolific panels (n = 1809 prior to data cleaning).

Study 2 was conducted online in 2023, with a quota sample of Spanish residents recruited by a market research company from proprietary panels (n = 1334 prior to data cleaning).

Sample socio-demographics are shown in Table 1 for participants without missing data for a given variable⁵. While budget constraints prevented collecting data from representative samples, the collected data exhibit good representation of the various socio-demographic categories.

Table 1: Sample socio-demographics

Variable	Category	Percent in sample	
		Study 1	Study 2
Gender	Female	49.36	51.24
	Male	49.80	48.46
	Non-binary, other	0.84	0.30
Age	18-29 years old	23.93	16.82
	30-39 years old	27.86	14.64
	40-49 years old	20.74	19.37
	50-59 years old	16.54	18.09
	Over 60 years of age	10.93	31.08
Education	Mandatory education	1.41	5.51
	Some high school	3.21	6.26
	Graduated high school	18.47	27.09
	Some college	18.36	12.00
	University degree	58.56	49.13
Income	Less than £19,000	28.63	
	£19,000 – £25,999	21.81	
	£26,000 – £39,000	27.33	
	More than £39,000	22.23	
	Less than 10,000 EUR		11.01
	10,000 – 19,999 EUR		19.24
	20,000 – 29,999 EUR		30.17
	More than 30,000 EUR		39.59
Type of residence	Apartment	19.55	59.43
	House	78.65	35.90
	Other	1.80	4.68
Home ownership	Rented home	34.00	22.01
	Own home	59.81	73.15
	Other	6.20	4.84
Household size	1 person	16.03	9.33
	2 people	31.49	28.22
	3 people	21.44	30.93
	4 people	21.16	25.21
	More than 4 people	9.88	6.32
Place of residence size	Less than 50,000 inhabitants	36.48	28.79
	50,000 – 300,000	36.86	35.91

⁵ “Income” and “region” had the largest amount of missing data among the socio-demographics, with 6.7 percent of participants in Study 1 and 5.3 percent of participants in Study 2 choosing not to report income, and 8.8 percent of participants in Study 1 and 5.0 percent of participants in Study 2 not reporting in which region they reside. In addition, 12.1 percent of participants “did not know or preferred not to say” their “place of residence size” in Study 1.

	inhabitants		
	More than 300,000 inhabitants	26.37	35.30
Region	East Midlands	8.31	
	East of England	7.76	
	Greater London	12.61	
	Northern Ireland	2.06	
	North East England	6.97	
	Scotland	9.64	
	South East England	16.37	
	South West England	10.07	
	Wales	5.94	
	West Midlands	10.61	
	Yorkshire and the Humber	9.64	
	Andalucía		14.75
	Aragón		2.60
	Canarias		3.39
	Cantabria		1.89
	Castilla y León		5.52
	Castilla-La Mancha		4.42
	Cataluña		17.51
	Comunidad de Madrid		20.43
	Comunidad Foral de Navarra		0.87
	Comunidad Valenciana		9.86
	Extremadura		2.21
	Galicia		6.31
	Islas Baleares		1.66
	La Rioja		0.63
	País Vasco		3.94
	Principado de Asturias		2.05
Región de Murcia		1.97	

3.2. Study materials and description of variables

Study materials for Studies 1 and 2 were partly identical, and we will therefore describe them jointly for the two studies, with substantive differences highlighted in the text. The surveys consisted of several parts or modules, which are described in what follows.

3.2.1. Preferences for energy services

We created a stated choice experiment in which each participant indicated their preferred electricity contracts in a series of eight choice scenarios (with one preferred contract picked out of three available options in each scenario). Sample choice scenario is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Example choice scenario

Energy service characteristics	Contract A	Contract B	Contract C (current contract)
Financial savings in your electricity bill:	0%	20%	0%
Share of electricity consumed by your household generated from renewable sources:	60%	80%	[Information displayed based on participant's response from a pre-experimental questionnaire.]
You can control your electrical appliances remotely via a mobile app:	Yes	No	[Information displayed based on participant's response from a pre-experimental questionnaire.]
Energy provider's control of your thermostat: - setting your thermostat to 18 °C - every day in winter between 17:00-20:00	Total control. Your electricity provider <u>can automatically</u> take control of your thermostat.	Partial control. Your electricity provider <u>can request</u> control of your thermostat via text message. You can accept or decline.	[Information displayed based on participant's response from a pre-experimental questionnaire.]

Contract C (see the rightmost column in Table 2) was based on information previously elicited from the participant about their current contract. This means that if participants preferred not to switch to an alternative contract A or B, they could always select their current contract instead.

Attributes of the contracts and their levels are shown in Table 3. We used a D-efficient experimental design with uninformative priors, which generates meaningful trade-offs between attributes while maintaining attribute-level balance in the data (Rose & Bliemer, 2009; Bliemer & Rose, 2010). The design featured a total of 24 choice scenarios that were subdivided into three blocks of eight scenarios each (with one block randomly assigned to each respondent).

Table 3: Attributes and attribute levels used in the choice experiment

Attribute (variable name)	Attribute description presented to participants	Levels
Financial savings	Financial savings in your electricity bill	0%
		5%
		10%
		20%
Renewable sources share	Share of electricity consumed by your household generated from renewable sources	40%
		60%
		80%
		100%
Remote control of appliances	You can control your electrical appliances remotely via a mobile app	No
		Yes
Energy provider control of thermostat	Energy provider's control of your thermostat - setting your thermostat to 18 °C - every day in winter between 17:00-20:00	None
		Partial control. Your electricity provider <u>can request</u> control of your thermostat via text message. You can accept or decline.
		Total control. Your electricity provider <u>can automatically</u> take control of your thermostat.

3.2.2. Preferences for energy monitoring apps

Data described in this section come from Study 2.

Participants were presented with one of two versions (randomly assigned) of a short description of a fictitious mobile phone app designed to “help people manage their electricity use”. Excerpts from the two versions of the app descriptions summarizing the app features read as follows:

“The app [version 1]:

- Tracks and displays energy consumption for each electrical device in your household in a user-friendly format.
- Shows you how much energy you used was generated from which energy source (e.g., coal, gas, nuclear, hydro, wind, solar).
- Based on your consumption data, the app can offer you tips on how to save energy. E.g., it can tell you what would be the best settings for your hot water tank to enjoy hot water as normal but save energy.”

“The app [version 2]:

- Tracks and displays energy consumption for each electrical device in your household in a user-friendly format.
- Shows you how much energy you used was generated from which energy source (e.g., coal, gas, nuclear, hydro, wind, solar).
- Based on your consumption data and current energy market and weather conditions, the app can offer you tips on how to use energy in such a way that the energy you use is primarily generated from renewable sources (e.g., wind, solar, hydro). E.g., it can tell you what would be the best settings for your hot water tank to enjoy hot water as normal while using mostly energy generated from renewable sources.”

Our research strategy consisted of eliciting participants’ perceptions of the app’s attributes and then testing whether these perceptions predict consumer interest in these products.

Perceptions of “environmental attributes” were measured with three items: “Using the app would help me lower my greenhouse gas emissions. Using the app would contribute to climate change mitigation. Using the app would contribute to energy conservation in my household.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”. The three items formed a reliable scale (Cronbach’s alpha = .87) and were averaged to compute the variable “environmental attributes”.

Perceptions of “instrumental attributes” were measured with three items with a common stem “Using the app would...” Response options for the first item ranged from: “cost me a lot of effort” (coded as 1) to “save me a lot of effort” (coded as 5). Response options for the second item ranged from: “cost me a lot of money” (coded as 1) to “save me a lot of money” (coded as 5). Response options for the third item ranged from: “make my life a lot less comfortable” (coded as 1) to “make my life a lot more comfortable” (coded as 5). The three items formed a reliable scale (Cronbach’s alpha = .80) and were averaged to compute the variable “instrumental attributes”.

Perceptions of “symbolic attributes” were measured with four items based on Noppers et al. (2015): “Using the app would give me social status. Using the app would say something positive about me. Using the app would fit with how I see myself. I can show who I am by using this app.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”. The four items formed a reliable scale (Cronbach’s alpha = .86) and were averaged to compute the variable “symbolic attributes”.

The dependent variable labeled “preferences for monitoring devices” was measured with a single item: “If this app would be offered to you, would you be interested in downloading it?” Responses were provided on a 4-point scale with the following response categories: “Yes” (coded as 4), “Probably yes, but I would first study the technical specifications in detail” (coded as 3), “Not sure – I would first like to study the technical specifications in detail” (coded as 2), and “No” (coded as 1).

3.2.3. Segmentation variables

We collected information on a broad range of consumer characteristics.

“Environmental concern” was measured with three items: “How concerned are you about environmental damage? How concerned are you about global warming? How concerned are you about extinction of animal species?” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “not at all concerned” to 5 = “extremely concerned”. The items were used as indicators of the latent variable “environmental concern” when testing predictions from section 2.2 in Studies 1 and 2, and were averaged to form a reliable scale “environmental concern” (Cronbach’s alpha = .88) when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5 in Study 2.

“Environmental identity” was measured with four items taken from Whitmarsh and O’Neill (2010): “I think of myself as an environmentally-friendly consumer. I think of myself as someone who is very concerned with environmental issues. I would be embarrassed to be seen as having an environmentally friendly lifestyle. I would not want my family or friends to think of me as someone who is concerned about environmental issues.” Responses to the first two items were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”, responses to the latter two items were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly agree” to 5 = “strongly disagree”. The first two items were used as indicators of the latent variable “environmental identity” when testing predictions from section 2.2 in Studies 1 and 2. The first two items were averaged to form a reliable scale “environmental identity” (Cronbach’s alpha = .78) when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5 in Study 2 (the four items did not form a reliable scale).

In Study 2, “innovativeness” was measured with three items based on Hurt et al. (1977): “I am generally cautious about accepting new ideas. I have to see other people use new inventions before I consider using them myself. I am skeptical to new inventions.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly agree” to 5 = “strongly disagree”. However, only the third item was used as a measure of innovativeness when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5, as the three items did not form a reliable scale.

“Personal norm” was measured with four items: “I feel a personal obligation to save electricity at home. I feel a personal obligation to invest in appliances and new technologies that can help me save electricity at home. I feel a personal obligation to protect the natural environment. I feel a personal obligation to behave in a climate-friendly way in everyday life.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”. The items were used as indicators of the latent variable “personal norm” when testing predictions from section 2.2 in Studies 1 and 2, and were averaged to form a reliable scale “personal norm” (Cronbach’s alpha = .85) when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5 in Study 2.

“Pro-environmental consumer habits” were measured with two items: “When there is a choice, I choose the product that contributes to the least amount of environmental damage. I have switched products for environmental reasons.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “never” to 5 = “always”. The items were used as indicators of the latent variable “pro-environmental consumer habits” when testing predictions from section 2.2 in Studies 1 and 2, and were averaged to form a reliable scale “pro-environmental consumer habits” (Cronbach’s alpha = .75) when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5 in Study 2.

“Descriptive social norm” was measured with four items: “People close to me save electricity at home. People close to me invest in appliances and new technologies that help them save electricity at home. People close to me protect the natural environment. People close to me behave in a

climate-friendly way in everyday life.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”. The items were used as indicators of the latent variable “descriptive social norm” when testing predictions from section 2.2 in Studies 1 and 2, and were averaged to form a reliable scale “descriptive social norm” (Cronbach’s alpha = .82) when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5 in Study 2.

“Injunctive social norm” was measured with four items: “People close to me expect me to save electricity at home. People close to me expect me to invest in appliances and new technologies that can help me save electricity at home. People close to me expect me to protect the natural environment. People close to me expect me to behave in a climate-friendly way in everyday life.” Responses were provided on 5-point scales ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”. The items were used as indicators of the latent variable “injunctive social norm” when testing predictions from section 2.2 in Studies 1 and 2, and were averaged to form a reliable scale “injunctive social norm” (Cronbach’s alpha = .87) when testing predictions from sections 2.4 and 2.5 in Study 2.

We in addition measured “gender”, “age”, “education”, “income”, “type of residence” (apartment, house, other), “home ownership” (rented, own), “household size”, “region” where the participant lives, “place of residence size” (ranging from less than 50,000 inhabitants to more than 300,000 inhabitants), and “preferred energy sources” (selection of multiple responses from the set coal, gas, hydro, nuclear, solar, and wind was possible).

4. Results

We organize the presentation of results so that it largely mirrors the presentation of research questions from section 2., with section 4.1 corresponding to section 2.1, section 4.2 corresponding to section 2.2, section 4.3 corresponding to section 2.3, and so on.

4.1. Consumer preferences for energy services: The role of service attributes

Table 4 provides answers to our Research question 1: How do attributes of energy services – in particular, attainable financial savings, share of electricity generated from renewable sources, remote control of household appliances, and energy provider’s ability to control the consumer’s thermostat during demand peaks – affect consumer preferences for the services?

Key findings can be found in rows 3-7. In both Spain and the UK, participants prefer energy services that promise greater financial savings (row 3) and larger shares of energy generated from renewables (row 4). In neither country did participants prefer services allowing them to remotely control their household appliances (row 5). Participants in the UK disliked services involving direct load control of their thermostat (rows 6 and 7), especially when they could not opt out of a given demand response event (row 7). Somewhat surprisingly, participants in Spain preferred services allowing their energy provider to control their thermostat in winter during the evening peak (rows 6 and 7). Predictions P1, P2 and P4 from section 2.1.2 are therefore supported by the data. Prediction P3 was not supported.

Table 4: Energy service attributes as predictors of preferences

Row	Parameter		Study 1 (UK sample)	Study 2 (Spanish sample)
			Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)
(1)	Alternative-specific constants (reference category: Contract C)	Contract A	1.089*** (17.31)	-0.242* (-2.55)
(2)		Contract B	0.852*** (13.97)	0.210** (2.78)
(3)	Financial savings		0.069*** (28.97)	0.051*** (19.12)
(4)	Renewable sources share		0.012*** (16.42)	0.015*** (14.25)
(5)	Remote control of appliances		-0.142*** (-4.66)	-0.434*** (-8.90)
(6)	Energy provider control of thermostat (reference category: None)	Partial	-0.465*** (-10.21)	0.683*** (9.41)
(7)		Total	-2.288*** (-35.81)	0.812*** (15.91)
(8)	sigma		0.816*** (28.24)	0.842*** (28.00)
Model summaries				
(9)	Participants		1654	893
(10)	Estimated parameters		8	8
(11)	Log likelihood at convergence		-9882.94	-6521.07
(12)	AIC		19781.89	13058.15
(13)	BIC		19841.81	13113.14

Notes: Results obtained using logit model with error component (Train, 2009). * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, two-tailed tests.

4.2. Consumer preferences for energy services: Exploring preference heterogeneity

Tables 5 and 6 provide answers, for the UK and Spanish samples, respectively, to our Research question 2: Do consumers differ in terms of the weight they place on the different attributes of energy services (specifically on financial savings, share of renewables, remote control of appliances, and on relinquishing control of thermostat during demand peaks)?

The tables present estimates from latent variable models, which include variations in preferences linked to socio-demographics (rows 8-13) and to attitudinal variables (rows 14-19). Estimates testing predictions from section 2.2.2 can therefore be found in rows 8-19 of Tables 5 and 6. Note that for identification reasons it was not possible to test all theoretically possible interactions.

In what follows, we discuss differences in how various consumer groups respond to the different energy service attributes.

Starting with the UK sample (Table 5), men derive greater utility from financial savings than women (fifth column, row 8). Otherwise there are no differences in how consumers respond to financial savings.

There are also no differences in how consumers respond to energy services offering increased shares of renewables (sixth column).

Younger consumers (seventh column, rows 9-11) derive greater utility from the ability to remotely control their household appliances than consumers above 50, and so do people with weaker environmental identity (seventh column, row 15).

Regarding preferences for direct load control, when opting out of load control events is possible, we observe that people below 30 are more accepting of direct load control than people above 50 (eighth column, row 9), and so are people with strong pro-environmental personal norms (eighth column, row 16), but also people with weak environmental identity (eighth column, row 15).

When opting out of load control events is not allowed, men (rightmost column, row 8), people below 50 (rightmost column, rows 9-11), and people with weaker environmental identity (rightmost column, row 15) are more accepting of direct load control.

Turning to the Spanish sample (Table 6), we see no socio-demographic differences in how consumers respond to energy service attributes. There are, nevertheless, some differences due to attitudinal factors.

In particular, consumers with stronger environmental identity (seventh column, row 15), but also consumers who have not developed sustainable consumption habits (seventh column, row 17) derive greater utility from being able to remotely control their household appliances. Note that environmental identity had the opposite effect on preferences for remote control of appliances in the UK (seventh column in Table 5, row 15) and in Spain.

There are almost no differences in terms of acceptance of partial direct load control (i.e., when opting out of load control events is possible), except for consumers with sustainable environmental habits who dislike this service feature (eighth column, row 17).

There are also almost no differences in terms of acceptance of total direct load control, except for consumers with strong environmental identity who dislike this service attribute (rightmost column, row 15).

In terms of predictions from section 2.2.2, these results mean that predictions P5, P12, P14, P18, P21-P23, P26, P27 received support at least in one of the studied countries.

Table 5: Socio-demographic and attitudinal differences in preferences for energy service attributes in Study 1 (UK sample)

Row	Parameter		Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Interaction with “financial savings”	Interaction with “renewable sources share”	Interaction with “remote control of appliances”	Interaction with “energy provider control of thermostat” (Partial vs. None)	Interaction with “energy provider control of thermostat” (Total vs. None)
				Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)
(1)	Alternative-specific constants (reference category: Contract C)	Contract A	1.085*** (14.51)					
(2)		Contract B	0.858*** (11.79)					
(3)	Financial savings		0.071*** (11.35)					
(4)	Renewable sources share		0.018*** (8.59)					
(5)	Remote control of appliances		-0.385*** (-4.51)					
(6)	Energy provider control of thermostat (reference category: None)	Partial	-0.913*** (-5.32)					
(7)		Total	-4.001*** (-14.91)					
(8)	Gender (reference category: female)	Male		0.019*** (3.78)	-0.001 (-0.37)	-0.124 (-1.81)	-0.053 (-0.35)	0.588** (2.70)
(9)	Age (reference category: above 50 years of age)	18-29 years old		0.002 (0.25)	-0.000 (-0.06)	0.229* (2.33)	0.650** (2.93)	0.961** (2.70)
(10)		30-39 years old		-0.005 (-0.65)	0.001 (0.36)	0.172 [†] (1.88)	0.233 (1.34)	0.502 [†] (1.93)
(11)		40-49 years old		-0.003 (-0.38)	-0.004 (-1.36)	0.211* (2.09)	0.304 (1.60)	0.597* (2.13)
(12)	Education (reference category: Some college)	Graduated high school or lower		-0.004 (-0.69)	-0.003 (-1.43)	0.061 (0.70)	0.193 (1.16)	0.388 (1.56)
(13)		Some college		-0.008 (-1.24)	-0.001 (-0.27)	0.031 (0.35)	0.103 (0.57)	0.189 (0.73)

	university degree)							
(14)	Environmental concern					0.033 (0.32)	0.031 (0.11)	0.121 (0.28)
(15)	Environmental identity					-0.222*** (-3.74)	-1.467*** (-18.17)	-2.212*** (-15.31)
(16)	Personal norm					-0.080 (-0.88)	0.523** (2.99)	0.395 (1.38)
(17)	Pro-environmental consumer habits					0.017 (0.14)	-0.178 (-0.5)	-0.583 (-0.94)
(18)	Descriptive social norm					0.059 (0.82)	-0.022 (-0.13)	0.033 (0.17)
(19)	Injunctive social norm					0.035 (0.48)	-0.199 (-1.07)	-0.043 (-0.18)
Model summary								
(20)	Participants	1654						
(21)	Estimated parameters	156						
(22)	Log likelihood at convergence	-43720.09						
(23)	AIC	87752.19						
(24)	BIC	88595.82						

Notes: Results from hybrid choice model estimated using simulated maximum likelihood. [†] $p < .06$, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, two-tailed tests. Estimates in rows 3-7 are main effects for the reference group; for main effects of service attributes in the sample as a whole see Table 4 instead.

Table 6: Socio-demographic and attitudinal differences in preferences for energy service attributes in Study 2 (Spanish sample)

Row	Parameter		Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Interaction with “financial savings”	Interaction with “renewable sources share”	Interaction with “remote control of appliances”	Interaction with “energy provider control of thermostat” (Partial vs. None)	Interaction with “energy provider control of thermostat” (Total vs. None)
				Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)	Estimate (rob. t-ratio)
(1)	Alternative-specific constants (reference category: Contract C)	Contract A	-0.121 (-1.09)					
(2)		Contract B	0.464*** (4.99)					
(3)	Financial savings		0.050*** (8.8)					
(4)	Renewable sources share		0.012*** (3.82)					
(5)	Remote control of appliances		-0.132 (-0.73)					
(6)	Energy provider control of thermostat (reference category: None)	Partial	0.676** (3.12)					
(7)		Total	0.800*** (5.47)					
(8)	Gender (reference category: female)	Male		0.007 (1.29)	0.003 (1.12)	-0.173 (-0.99)	-0.286 (-1.35)	-0.148 (-1.17)
(9)	Age (reference category: above 50 years of age)	18-29 years old		-0.011 (-1.42)	-0.002 (-0.44)	0.015 (0.05)	-0.434 (-1.20)	-0.140 (-0.76)
(10)		30-39 years old		-0.006 (-0.73)	0.005 (1.15)	-0.230 (-1.00)	-0.367 (-1.47)	0.062 (0.31)
(11)		40-49 years old			0.004 (0.57)	0.005 (1.29)	-0.199 (-0.82)	0.260 (0.86)
(12)	Education (reference category: university)	Graduated high school or lower		0.002 (0.35)	-0.004 (-1.24)	0.151 (0.72)	0.206 (0.70)	0.083 (0.58)

	degree)							
(13)		Some college		-0.006 (-0.69)	-0.003 (-0.62)	-0.021 (-0.08)	0.198 (0.66)	0.288 (1.29)
(14)	Environmental concern					-0.081 (-0.25)	-0.088 (-0.25)	0.001 (0.01)
(15)	Environmental identity					0.823* (2.27)	0.097 (0.14)	-0.909*** (-3.66)
(16)	Personal norm					-0.118 (-0.61)	-0.032 (-0.16)	0.039 (0.24)
(17)	Pro-environmental consumer habits					-0.831* (-2.40)	-1.550*** (-10.92)	-0.409 (-1.09)
(18)	Descriptive social norm					0.230 (1.36)	0.213 (0.92)	-0.245 (-1.12)
(19)	Injunctive social norm					0.215 (1.59)	-0.070 (-0.32)	-0.024 (-0.18)
Model summary								
(20)	Participants	893						
(21)	Estimated parameters	156						
(22)	Log likelihood at convergence	-23614.68						
(23)	AIC	47541.35						
(24)	BIC	48289.31						

Notes: Results from hybrid choice model estimated using simulated maximum likelihood. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, two-tailed tests. Estimates in rows 3-7 are main effects for the reference group; for main effects of service attributes in the sample as a whole see Table 4 instead.

4.3. Consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices: The role of perceived product attributes

Models 1 and 2 in Table 7 show results of analyses addressing our Research question 3: How do perceived attributes of apps monitoring energy consumption of electrical appliances in one's household – specifically environmental, instrumental, and symbolic attributes – influence consumer preferences for such devices?

In Model 1, we regress “preferences for monitoring devices” on “environmental attributes”, “instrumental attributes”, and “symbolic attributes”. In Model 2, we in addition control for a suite of consumer characteristics.

Models 3 and 4 are used to address Research questions 4 and 5, and these results will be discussed in sections 4.4 and 4.5, respectively. In Model 3, we regress “preferences for monitoring devices” on consumer characteristics. In Model 4, we regress “preferences for monitoring devices” on “environmental attributes”, “instrumental attributes”, and “symbolic attributes”, on consumer characteristics, and on interactions of product attributes with consumer characteristics. Note that due to inclusion of interaction terms in Model 4, coefficients in rows 1-39 in this model should not be compared to coefficients in Models 1-3.

Turning to our Research question 3, we see from Model 1 (rows 2-4) that perceptions of environmental, instrumental, as well as symbolic attributes increase interest in downloading the energy monitoring app. This result holds also when controlling for participants' background characteristics (see Model 2, rows 2-4). The role of product attributes is sizeable, as they jointly explain almost 43% of variance in preferences (see Model 1, row 143).

In terms of predictions from section 2.3.3, this means that all three predictions (P29, P30, P31) are supported by the data.

Table 7: Perceived product attributes and consumer characteristics as predictors of preferences for energy monitoring devices

Row	Parameter		Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
			Estimate (std. error)	Estimate (std. error)	Estimate (std. error)	Estimate (std. error)
(1)	Constant		0.123 (0.084)	-0.106 (0.184)	0.341 (0.211)	0.755 (0.760)
(2)	Environmental attributes		0.197*** (0.026)	0.170*** (0.029)		0.425 (0.267)
(3)	Instrumental attributes		0.316*** (0.029)	0.302*** (0.032)		0.187 (0.335)
(4)	Symbolic attributes		0.231*** (0.028)	0.210*** (0.032)		-0.236 (0.298)
(5)	Environmental concern			0.097* (0.039)	0.218*** (0.045)	-0.064 (0.153)
(6)	Environmental identity			-0.041 (0.036)	-0.005 (0.042)	0.148 (0.157)
(7)	Personal norm			0.026 (0.037)	0.084 (0.045)	0.029 (0.147)
(8)	Pro-environmental consumer habits			-0.037 (0.034)	0.015 (0.038)	0.056 (0.138)
(9)	Descriptive norm			0.038 (0.038)	0.131** (0.047)	0.079 (0.185)
(10)	Injunctive norm			-0.035 (0.038)	0.082 (0.046)	-0.060 (0.176)
(11)	Innovativeness			0.067** (0.020)	0.104*** (0.023)	0.047 (0.087)
(12)	Gender (reference category: male)	Female		0.038 (0.039)	0.108* (0.047)	-0.216 (0.189)
(13)		Non-binary, other		-0.021 (0.766)	0.454 (0.701)	
(14)	Age			-0.085*** (0.016)	-0.147*** (0.018)	-0.309*** (0.082)
(15)	Education			0.013 (0.018)	0.019 (0.021)	0.031 (0.078)
(16)	Income			0.046* (0.022)	0.057* (0.027)	-0.038 (0.101)
(17)	Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	House		-0.001 (0.045)	0.064 (0.055)	-0.391 (0.221)
(18)		Other		-0.027 (0.109)	-0.051 (0.118)	0.206 (0.476)
(19)	Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Own home		0.014 (0.048)	0.030 (0.058)	0.312 (0.245)
(20)		Other		-0.057 (0.125)	-0.125 (0.148)	0.171 (0.571)
(21)	Household size			0.039* (0.019)	0.065** (0.023)	0.058 (0.091)
(22)	Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Aragón		0.090 (0.138)	0.064 (0.180)	-0.138 (0.537)
(23)		Canarias		0.197 (0.121)	0.253 (0.135)	0.855 (0.810)
(24)		Cantabria		0.140 (0.155)	0.151 (0.171)	-0.466 (0.692)
(25)		Castilla y León		0.076 (0.097)	0.078 (0.113)	-0.197 (0.453)
(26)		Castilla-La Mancha		0.091 (0.107)	0.119 (0.127)	0.309 (0.600)
(27)		Cataluña		0.032 (0.072)	-0.017 (0.086)	-0.206 (0.331)
(28)		Comunidad de Madrid		0.059 (0.065)	0.022 (0.078)	-0.179 (0.289)
(29)		Comunidad Foral		0.432* (0.203)	0.305 (0.172)	2.614** (0.810)

		de Navarra				
(30)		Comunidad Valenciana		0.072 (0.081)	0.006 (0.098)	0.064 (0.320)
(31)		Extremadura		-0.096 (0.144)	-0.209 (0.169)	0.069 (0.650)
(32)		Galicia		0.049 (0.086)	-0.056 (0.106)	0.330 (0.491)
(33)		Islas Baleares		-0.057 (0.103)	-0.073 (0.161)	-0.079 (0.453)
(34)		La Rioja		0.047 (0.083)	0.073 (0.128)	-0.348 (0.847)
(35)		País Vasco		-0.008 (0.110)	-0.079 (0.134)	0.124 (0.489)
(36)		Principado de Asturias		0.064 (0.134)	0.150 (0.156)	0.017 (0.916)
(37)		Región de Murcia		0.162 (0.122)	0.071 (0.145)	0.462 (0.566)
(38)	Place of residence size (reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	50,000 – 300,000 inhabitants		0.009 (0.050)	0.089 (0.061)	-0.237 (0.239)
(39)		More than 300,000 inhabitants		-0.001 (0.055)	0.056 (0.066)	0.114 (0.278)
(40)	Environmental attributes by Environmental concern					0.102* (0.051)
(41)	Instrumental attributes by Environmental concern					-0.041 (0.051)
(42)	Symbolic attributes by Environmental concern					-0.007 (0.050)
(43)	Environmental attributes by Environmental identity					0.002 (0.048)
(44)	Instrumental attributes by Environmental identity					-0.083 (0.052)
(45)	Symbolic attributes by Environmental identity					0.019 (0.055)
(46)	Environmental attributes by Personal norm					0.000 (0.056)
(47)	Instrumental attributes by Personal norm					-0.005 (0.062)
(48)	Symbolic attributes by Personal norm					-0.005 (0.060)
(49)	Environmental attributes by Pro-environmental consumer habits					-0.056 (0.048)
(50)	Instrumental attributes by Pro-environmental consumer habits					0.061 (0.049)
(51)	Symbolic attributes by Pro-environmental consumer habits					-0.025 (0.050)
(52)	Environmental attributes by Descriptive norm					-0.108* (0.054)
(53)	Instrumental attributes by Descriptive norm					-0.017 (0.071)
(54)	Symbolic attributes by Descriptive norm					0.137** (0.052)
(55)	Environmental attributes by Injunctive norm					0.026 (0.050)
(56)	Instrumental attributes by Injunctive norm					0.003 (0.062)

(57)	Symbolic attributes by Injunctive norm					-0.027 (0.043)
(58)	Environmental attributes by Innovativeness					-0.022 (0.029)
(59)	Instrumental attributes by Innovativeness					0.011 (0.031)
(60)	Symbolic attributes by Innovativeness					0.015 (0.030)
(61)	Environmental attributes by Gender (reference category: male)	Female				-0.041 (0.059)
(62)	Instrumental attributes by Gender (reference category: male)	Female				0.188** (0.066)
(63)	Symbolic attributes by Gender (reference category: male)	Female				-0.080 (0.063)
(64)	Environmental attributes by Age					-0.032 (0.026)
(65)	Instrumental attributes by Age					0.076** (0.027)
(66)	Symbolic attributes by Age					0.023 (0.023)
(67)	Environmental attributes by Education					0.000 (0.027)
(68)	Instrumental attributes by Education					0.010 (0.032)
(69)	Symbolic attributes by Education					-0.017 (0.030)
(70)	Environmental attributes by Income					0.026 (0.033)
(71)	Instrumental attributes by Income					-0.039 (0.036)
(72)	Symbolic attributes by Income					0.039 (0.034)
(73)	Environmental attributes by Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	House				-0.100 (0.074)
(74)	Instrumental attributes by Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	House				0.120 (0.081)
(75)	Symbolic attributes by Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	House				0.102 (0.074)
(76)	Environmental attributes by Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	Other				-0.044 (0.158)
(77)	Instrumental attributes by Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	Other				0.152 (0.168)
(78)	Symbolic attributes by Type of residence (reference category: apartment)	Other				-0.216 (0.170)
(79)	Environmental attributes by Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Own home				0.057 (0.068)
(80)	Instrumental attributes by Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Own home				-0.034 (0.081)
(81)	Symbolic attributes by Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Own home				-0.118 (0.075)

(82)	Environmental attributes by Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Other				-0.329* (0.156)
(83)	Instrumental attributes by Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Other				-0.127 (0.206)
(84)	Symbolic attributes by Home ownership (reference category: rented home)	Other				0.441* (0.172)
(85)	Environmental attributes by Household size					0.000 (0.027)
(86)	Instrumental attributes by Household size					-0.010 (0.032)
(87)	Symbolic attributes by Household size					0.005 (0.030)
(88)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Aragón				-0.167 (0.250)
(89)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Aragón				-0.099 (0.158)
(90)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Aragón				0.380 (0.301)
(91)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Canarias				0.011 (0.142)
(92)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Canarias				-0.287 (0.212)
(93)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Canarias				0.102 (0.211)
(94)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Cantabria				0.120 (0.438)
(95)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Cantabria				0.132 (0.432)
(96)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Cantabria				-0.103 (0.257)
(97)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Castilla y León				0.139 (0.146)
(98)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Castilla y León				0.135 (0.145)
(99)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Castilla y León				-0.232 (0.148)
(100)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Castilla-La Mancha				0.281 (0.152)
(101)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Castilla-La				-0.016 (0.167)

	Andalucía)	Mancha				
(102)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Castilla-La Mancha				-0.365* (0.181)
(103)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Cataluña				0.120 (0.107)
(104)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Cataluña				-0.004 (0.122)
(105)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Cataluña				-0.067 (0.115)
(106)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad de Madrid				0.021 (0.096)
(107)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad de Madrid				0.061 (0.111)
(108)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad de Madrid				-0.019 (0.113)
(109)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad Foral de Navarra				-0.186 (0.272)
(110)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad Foral de Navarra				-0.449 (0.253)
(111)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad Foral de Navarra				0.041 (0.240)
(112)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad Valenciana				-0.098 (0.106)
(113)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad Valenciana				0.213 (0.133)
(114)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Comunidad Valenciana				-0.112 (0.129)
(115)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Extremadura				-0.367 (0.227)
(116)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Extremadura				0.205 (0.421)
(117)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Extremadura				0.161 (0.291)
(118)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Galicia				0.136 (0.111)
(119)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Galicia				-0.212 (0.149)

	Andalucía)					
(120)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Galicia				-0.028 (0.134)
(121)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Islas Baleares				0.046 (0.135)
(122)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Islas Baleares				0.019 (0.150)
(123)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Islas Baleares				-0.041 (0.163)
(124)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	La Rioja				0.174 (0.290)
(125)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	La Rioja				0.174 (0.185)
(126)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	La Rioja				-0.284 (0.243)
(127)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	País Vasco				-0.064 (0.145)
(128)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	País Vasco				-0.075 (0.158)
(129)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	País Vasco				0.096 (0.134)
(130)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Principado de Asturias				0.158 (0.235)
(131)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Principado de Asturias				-0.069 (0.234)
(132)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Principado de Asturias				-0.099 (0.178)
(133)	Environmental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Región de Murcia				0.081 (0.185)
(134)	Instrumental attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Región de Murcia				-0.190 (0.212)
(135)	Symbolic attributes by Region (reference category: Andalucía)	Región de Murcia				-0.003 (0.227)
(136)	Environmental attributes by Place of residence size (reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	50,000 – 300,000 inhabitants				-0.107 (0.079)
(137)	Instrumental attributes by Place of residence size	50,000 – 300,000				0.134 (0.090)

	(reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	inhabitants				
(138)	Symbolic attributes by Place of residence size (reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	50,000 – 300,000 inhabitants				0.057 (0.090)
(139)	Environmental attributes by Place of residence size (reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	More than 300,000 inhabitants				-0.155 (0.093)
(140)	Instrumental attributes by Place of residence size (reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	More than 300,000 inhabitants				0.095 (0.100)
(141)	Symbolic attributes by Place of residence size (reference category: less than 50,000 inhabitants)	More than 300,000 inhabitants				0.038 (0.088)
Model summaries						
(142)	Participants		1331	1164	1165	1161
(143)	R^2		.426	.489	.267	.540

Notes: Results of linear regression analyses with robust standard errors. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, two-tailed tests.

4.4. Consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices: The role of consumer characteristics

Evidence concerning our Research question 4, namely whether consumer characteristics predict preferences for energy monitoring devices, comes mainly from Model 3 in Table 7, in which we regress “preferences for monitoring devices” on consumer characteristics.

We see that environmental concern (Model 3, row 5), pro-environmental descriptive normative beliefs (Model 3, row 9), innovativeness (Model 3, row 11), self-reported female gender (Model 3, row 12), younger age (Model 3, row 14), higher income (Model 3, row 16), and larger household size (Model 3, row 21) are all associated with stronger preferences for energy monitoring apps⁶. In terms of predictions from section 2.3.4, this means that predictions P32, P34, P37, P39, P40, P42, and P45 are supported by the data.

In contrast, holding other individual characteristics in Model 3 constant, environmental identity, personal norms, injunctive norms, and consumer habits were not predictive of preferences for energy monitoring apps. Neither were education, type of residence, home ownership, urbanicity (“place of residence size”) or region.

Overall, the role of individual consumer characteristics is fairly sizeable, accounting for 27% of variance in preferences (see Model 3, row 143), and explaining about 6% of variance in preferences on top of perceptions of product attributes (see Models 1 and 2, row 143).

4.5. Consumer preferences for energy monitoring devices: Exploring preference heterogeneity

Rows 40-141 in Model 4 (in Table 7) help answer our Research question 5: Do consumers differ in terms of the weight they place on the different attributes of energy monitoring devices (specifically on environmental, instrumental, and symbolic attributes)?

It is apparent from Model 4 that in most instances this is not the case. Nevertheless, those differences in how consumers react to product attributes that do exist are not unimportant, uniquely explaining about 5% of variance in preferences (see Models 2 and 4, row 143).

In particular, environmental attributes of energy monitoring apps are more important to people with stronger environmental concern (row 40) and to people with weaker descriptive norms (row 52), and less important to people living rent-free⁷ than to renters (row 82).

⁶ In Model 2, we additionally control for product perceptions. Once product perceptions are held constant, descriptive norms and gender no longer significantly predict preferences.

⁷ While we do not have more concrete information on their living situation, presumably these could often be people living rent-free with their family, partner or friends.

Instrumental attributes are more important to women than to men (row 62) and their importance is increasing with age (row 65).

Symbolic attributes are more important to people with stronger descriptive norms (row 54) and to people living rent-free compared to renters (row 84).

We see virtually no regional differences in how people respond to product attributes (the interaction in row 102 should not be over-interpreted).

The above findings mean that of the predictions in section 2.3.5, only predictions P48, P53, P60, P71, P72, P85, P92 (and partially P94) are supported by the data.

5. Discussion and conclusions

Which consumer segments are likely to adopt energy services and products that can contribute to demand flexibility in an energy system increasingly reliant on intermittent energy sources? And why may they be willing to do so?

In the present report we broke down these two core questions into several smaller ones and derived and tested close to a hundred predictions using data from two online studies conducted in Spain and the United Kingdom.

We identified people with **strong environmental concern** and those who see others around them behaving pro-environmentally as one consumer group that is likely to adopt innovative energy monitoring and management technologies. Consumers who are **more innovative** are also more likely to adopt. These findings are broadly consistent with prior research (Noppers et al., 2015; van der Werff & Steg, 2016; Hmielowski et al., 2019). **Women, younger people, wealthier consumers, and members of larger households** may also be more likely to adopt energy monitoring apps.

Perceived attributes of energy monitoring apps predicted a large portion of variation in willingness to adopt. The studied attributes involved functional features (comfort, convenience, and financial savings), positive environmental externalities (e.g., lowering greenhouse gas emissions), and the app's ability to meet people's symbolic motives (e.g., self-expression). These findings reinforce the message from other studies that it is not solely the functional features that lead people to adopt eco-friendly technologies (Noppers et al., 2014, 2015; Whittle et al., 2020).

There are interesting differences in how different types of consumers respond to perceived attributes of energy monitoring apps. In particular, gender, age, environmental concern, social norms, and partly also home ownership, influence how consumers respond to certain product attributes. For instance, **environmentally conscious consumers** see greater value in products which they perceive to have a positive impact on the environment. **Women and older people find functional benefits of energy monitoring devices**, such as increased comfort and convenience, more important than men and younger people.

The ways in which consumer and product characteristics interact are generally not well understood. Early attempts to elucidate this question are reported by Noppers et al. (2015, 2019) and Tu et al. (2021). While our findings indicate somewhat limited importance of matching product attributes (or their marketing) to specific consumer segments, it is too early to draw definitive conclusions due to the limited evidence base. The present study provides a useful template for systematically exploring the interplay of consumer and product characteristics in subsequent research.

In two choice experiments, we further confirm that **people prefer electricity contracts offering an increased share of renewable energy and financial savings**. People in the UK are averse to direct load control, but people in Spain are not, at least in the context of allowing their energy provider to lower their thermostat settings during evening winter demand peaks. The acceptance of direct load control in our Spanish sample contrasts especially with findings from countries with harsher climates in Northern Europe (Broberg & Persson, 2016; Ruokamo et al., 2019), suggesting that researchers and policy makers should pay close **attention to regional differences** in optimal design of **demand response schemes**.

Socio-demographics played virtually no role in driving preferences for energy service attributes in the Spanish choice experiment, but they did in the UK. In particular, men respond more strongly than women to offers involving financial savings, younger consumers respond more positively to energy services bundled with technological innovations (we focused specifically on giving consumers the option to remotely control their household appliances). And **men and younger people are also more accepting of direct load control**. Our finding that men may be more accepting of direct load control concurs with Broberg and Persson (2016), but our finding that younger people may respond more positively to direct load control contrasts partly with former research from other countries (Broberg and Persson, 2016; Curtis et al., 2020; Srivastava et al., 2020; Lehmann et al., 2022a). In addition, recall that in Spain we did not observe any differences in preferences across socio-demographic groups. Taken together, these findings point to the need to carefully consider regional differences in how socio-demographic factors influence willingness to engage in demand response, and equally importantly underscore the need for replicating early findings. A limitation of our studies is that for statistical reasons we were only able to include a narrower selection of socio-demographics in our models, leaving other important segmentation variables, such as income, to future research.

Attitudinal variables also appeared to shape consumer preferences for energy service attributes. Most importantly, environmental identity and pro-environmental consumption habits undermined people's willingness to accept direct load control of their thermostats during demand peaks. Such a pattern is consistent with negative spillover (Truelove et al., 2014). On the other hand, perceived obligation to behave pro-environmentally (i.e., personal norm) strengthened people's willingness to accept direct load control (at least in the UK).

Thus, **people not yet engaged in sustainable consumption**, not yet seeing themselves as particularly **pro-environmental**, **men**, **younger people**, and those feeling an obligation to behave more pro-environmentally, appear to form consumer segments with a **greater willingness to engage in demand response**.

Our findings need to be interpreted with care, in light of two main limitations:

One limitation being that we conducted our investigations in only two countries. Spain was selected as it is one of the project's pilot countries. UK was selected on more pragmatic grounds, namely due to better access to a large enough sample than would be possible in Austria or Finland (our two other pilot countries), while being relatively similar to Austria and Finland in terms of climate. Previous research suggests that some (see esp. section 2.2.1) but not all (see esp. section 2.2.2) patterns of consumer preferences generalize well across different countries. Our studies looking at the two countries also uncovered important cross-country differences in preferences. A large-scale replication of our studies involving a broad selection of European countries seems to be needed to confirm or qualify the generality of preferences of energy consumers in Europe.

In addition, all choices made in our surveys were hypothetical and/or self-reported. This does not necessarily mean that the results are skewed in a particular direction (Vesely & Klöckner, 2020), but it could mean participants' responses involved a degree of unsystematic noise (Kormos & Gifford, 2014). Additional support for our conclusions may be obtained from future studies involving purchasing and contractual decisions in naturalistic field settings.

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